

Chemistry of Bisphenol-A-Furfural Resin Formation

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Bisphenol-alcohol analogues of furfuraldehyde were prepared by condensing 1:1 mole of bisphenol-A and furfural using both 1% phosphoric acid and 2% sodium hydroxide condensing agents, in ethyl alcohol medium, at reflux temperature. The physical and chemical analysis of the resin intermediates were carried out. Novolak and resole types of bisphenol-A-furfural resins were prepared using 1:1 and 1:2 mole ratio of bisphenol-furfural polymer was prepared by heating the resole at 150° for 2 hr. Infrared and NMR spectra of the resins were recorded. Possible mechanism of resin formation reaction is described, IR and NMR spectral investigations of various bisphenol-A-furfural resins are discussed in detail. It is found that the bisphenol-A-furfural resin formation reaction takes place in similar manner as phenol formaldehyde reaction with initial formation of bisphenol-alcohol analogue of furfural. The bisphenol-alcohol analogue further reacts to obtain furamethane linkages. However evidence for furfuryl ether formation is absent, indicating the absence of reaction of bisphenol-alcohol analogue of furfural with itself to form furfuryl ether.

It is a well established fact that during the preparation of phenol-aldehyde resins, phenol alcohols, dihydroxydiphenylmethane and dimethylene ethers are formed at various stages depending upon reaction conditions.¹ Although various physical and chemical methods have been used to study the chemistry of resin formation, infrared spectra and proton magnetic resonance spectra appear to be by far the best.

The chemical nature of furfuraldehyde suggests its use in preparation of materials similar to that of phenol-formaldehyde resins. Furfural probably has better commercial importance in the manufacture of phenoplast, compared to all other higher aldehydes, due to definite advantages over conventional formaldehyde.² Although furfural is used as special purpose resin former in many industrial applications, hardly any attempts have been made to understand the chemistry of resin formation. Phenol alcohol analogue of furfural was however isolated by A. E. Porai Koshutz^{3,4} and formation of dihydroxydiphenyl furamethane was suggested by A. J. Norton⁵ in the case of phenol-furfural resins.

In the light of this the possibility of using newer intermediates for preparation of phenol aldehyde resins with improved thermal, chemical, mechanical and electrical properties was considered and use of p-p dihydroxydiphenylalkaline and furfural suggested itself and a new resin based on bisphenol-A and furfural was prepared and evaluated for its applications in molding powders, lamination and casting.^{6,7,8} The chemistry of bisphenol-A-furfural resin formation reaction was also studied with help of IR and NMR and results have been summarized in the following pages.

Experimental

Bisphenol-A, furfuraldehyde and other chemicals required for the investigation were obtained from a local manufacturer, Messrs. Natson Manufacturing Co. Private Limited and B. D. H. respectively.

Preparation of Phenol-alcohol Analogue of Bisphenol-A-Furfural : 85.5 g of crystallized bisphenol-A was taken in a 500 ml round bottom flask with standard joints. 36 g of freshly double distilled furfural and 1.7 g of A. R. NaOH dissolved in 250 ml ethanol was added to the flask. The mixture was allowed to reflux for 3 hr. cooled to room temperature and neutralized to pH 7 with adequate amount of dil. HCl. Ethyl alcohol was carefully distilled under vacuum at 50°. The condensation reaction product was extracted with hot distilled water in order to separate hot water soluble resin intermediates from insoluble resin. The product was recrystallized from hot distilled water. The yield of intermediate was 12.71% on wt. of bisphenol-A-taken. In similar way the intermediate product using 1% phosphoric acid was prepared. The yield was 9.93%.

Preparation of Resin : The resin formation reactions were carried out in three-neck quick fit glass apparatus with water condenser, two loop stirrer, heating and cooling system and vacuum connections. The alkali catalyzed resin was prepared by condensing 85.5 g of bisphenol-A with 36 g of furfural for 2.5 hr, using 5% sodium hydroxide catalyst on wt. of bisphenol-A at 120°. The product was red brown coloured solid, fusible and soluble resin. The resole type resin was prepared by condensing 114 g of bisphenol-A and 96.1 g of furfural for 2.5 hr using 5% sodium hydroxide condensing agent on wt. of bisphenol-A at 100°. The product was red brown coloured liquid resin. The crosslinked polymer was obtained by heating the resole type resin in oven at 150° for 2 hr. The typical acid catalyzed resin was prepared by condensing 85.5 g of bisphenol-A with 36 g of furfural for 2.5 hr. using 3% HCl condensing agent at 100°. The product was steel grey-black coloured solid resin.

Characterization of Resin Intermediates : The intermediate prepared using alkali catalyzed reaction was lemon yellow, having needle shaped crystals with

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m. p. 152°, while that produced from acid catalyzed reaction gave light-grey crystals of m p. 150°. Both products were odourless.

When the intermediates were heated in a clean test tube, resulted information of corresponding resin with evolution of little vapours.

Elemental analysis of both the intermediates were carried out for C, H and O using microanalytical methods. (Found : alkali catalyzed C, 78.0, O, 14.8, H, 7.2 per cent. Calcd. alkali catalyzed (Furamethane structure). C, 74.98, O, 6.00 H. 19.04 per cent)

Calcd. alkali catalyzed (Furfural ether structure) C, 76.17, O, 17.76, H 3.07.

(Found : acid catalyzed C, 79.0, O, 12.8, H, 8.2 per cent) Calcd. acid catalyzed C, 78.97, O, 14.81, H, 6.22 per cent)

A volumetric method based on phthalic anhydride in pyridine was used for estimation of secondary alcohol groups present in resin intermediates⁸. Percentage hydroxyl equivalent for acid and alkali catalyzed intermediates were found to be 5.1% and 8.2% respectively.

The molecular weight of resin intermediates was determined by modified Hill-Baldes⁹⁻¹² vapour pressure apparatus. (Model 115 Hitachi Perkin Elmer N. 6058 I E-4). Benzil was used as internal standard and acetone was used as solvent. The mol. wt. was found to be 319 for acid catalyzed and 411 for alkali catalyzed intermediates.

Spectral Study of Bisphenol-A-Furfural Resins :
A thin film of resin was prepared on the prism of Perkin Elmer Model 21 IR spectrophotometer, using resin solution in absolute methanol. The IR spectra were recorded as shown in Figs 1-3. Infrared spectra of crosslinked polymer was taken in KBr pallet as shown in Fig. 4.

High Resolution Varian Associate A-60 NMR spectrometer operating at 60 M cycles/sec. was employed for NMR study. Trimethylsilane (0.5% by vol) was used as internal standard. Resin concentration was kept within the range 5-22% by vol. Sweep rates were in the range of 1 to 4 cycles/sec/sec. and applied RF field in the range of 0.1 to 0.5 maguss. Aceton was used as solvent since the resin was insoluble in usual solvents like CHCl₃ and CCL₄ and the chemical shift of acetone did not interfere with the chemical shifts due to the resin. NMR spectra are shown in Fig. 5 and 6.

Results and Discussion

As in case of any phenol-aldehyde reactions the intermediates of resin formation seems to be phenol alcohols. It is evident from the physical and chemical analysis of the intermediates of resin formation that in both alkali and acid catalysed reactions bisphenol-A-alcohol analogue of furfural are formed. This is supported by molecular weight and estimation of secondary alcohol groups. Though the elemental analysis is to some extent agreeing in acid catalyzed reaction in case of alkali catalyzed products. The furamethane structure gives analysis which varies to a large extent. On the contrary if one calculates on the basis of furfuryl ether structure the values are nearer. The IR and NMR spectra however do not show any evidence for the ether structure and furamethane structure has to be accepted. In this case it could be concluded that the variation is observed and calculated values should be mainly as a result of the moisture observed by the material.

As in the case of phenol-formaldehyde condensation reaction the bisphenol-A-furfural condensation probably may take place in different ways as follows :

(a) By the condensation of bisphenol-alcohol analogue of furfural with bisphenol-A forming furamethane linkages at ortho position.

(b) By the condensation of bisphenol-alcohol analogue of furfural with itself, forming ether linkage.

Although arsenic trichloride can be used as internal standard for NMR spectral studies of these resins, the

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(c) By the condensation of bisphenol-alcohol analogue of furfural with itself forming furamethane linkage with evolution of furfural and water.

liberation of HCl from solvent may cause difficulties. In both the NMR spectra (Fig. 5 and 6) the spinning said bands are present which shows the complexity of

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However, the absence of IR band at 9.4 micron in novolak type resin (Fig. 1) indicates the absence of ether formation by reaction (b), while a small shoulder in resole type of resin indicates that there may be presence of ether linkage. Both the IR spectra (Fig. 1 and 2) show IR bands for aliphatic hydroxyl group, hence the presence of furfuryl carbinol group is confirmed. The IR spectra of crosslinked bisphenol-A-furfural resin (Fig. 4) indicates that both the benzene ring as well as furan ring structure take part in crosslinkage and phenolic hydroxyl group are involved to a limited extent.

the structure of bisphenol-A-furfural resins. The NMR peaks of alkali catalyzed product are more broadened than acid catalyzed resin, indicating that molecular size of alkali catalyzed resin is greater than acid catalyzed product. The larger molecular size of alkali catalyzed resin has less molecular freedom hence may limit complete motional narrowing of the line width. It is likely that bands due to furan ring interfere with the bands due to aromatic ring. NMR bands near chemical shift equivalent to 4 ppm (δ) are found to possess high intensity in case of alkali catalyzed product than

acid catalyzed product and lead to the possibility of more furamethane linkages in alkali catalyzed resin.

According to H. A. Szymanski^{1,3} the ordered and disordered resin can be evaluated by the position of hydroxyl proton signal. In case of acid catalyzed resin the presence of hydroxyl signal at chemical shift equivalent to 8 ppm (δ) indicate that the polymerization takes place at random and that there is little or no hydrogen bonding present, while in case of alkali catalyzed resin the hydroxyl proton signal remains superimposed beneath the ring proton signal, indicating the presence of hydrogen bonding between the phenolic hydroxyl and furan ring. The absence of hydroxyl proton signal at chemical shift equivalent to 8 ppm (δ) in alkali catalyzed resin, confirms the hydrogen bonding. The hydrogen bonding may be between furan ring and phenolic hydroxyl proton. Thus in case of alkali catalyzed resin the polymerization takes place in regular fashion, forming ortho linked polymer. Ether linkage is absent in both acid and alkali catalyzed resins, since there is no NMR signal at chemical shift equal to 4.5 ppm (δ). One can therefore, suggest that in case of novolak type bisphenol-A-furfural resins, the furfural carbinol does not react with itself to form ether linkages.

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